

Dynamics of cross-hatch patterns in heteroepitaxy

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Regular surface undulations, called cross-hatch patterns, appearing at the free surface of lattice-mismatched heteroepitaxial films are a key signature of plastic relaxation. Here we show that the dynamics of cross-hatch formation is accurately described by a continuum model based on strain-mediated surface diffusion, provided that a realistic distribution of dislocations is considered. We demonstrate quantitative agreement between our time-dependent simulations and dedicated atomic force microscopy experiments on $\text{Si}_{0.92}\text{Ge}_{0.08}$ films grown on Si(001) at various thicknesses, finally shedding light on the origin and on the dynamical behavior of a widely-investigated pattern, first observed more than half a century ago.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The advancement of the microelectronic industry has relied on the aggressive downscaling of the size typically featured by devices in the silicon-based complementary metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS) technology, known as the "more Moore" approach. However, since the "standard" MOS transistor architecture cannot be miniaturized beyond a certain size, the microelectronic industry has pursued different solutions, ranging from different transistor architectures (such as multiple gates¹, fin-FET², gate-all around³) to the heterointegration of different semiconductors to be used as base material for p- and n- MOSFET channels⁴ or as stressors for Si⁵. The possibility to heterointegrate advanced materials on Si substrates during the front end of the line stages (FEOL) of the manufacturing process, has prompted a wealth of studies aiming at achieving high quality of the heterolayer while preserving its manufacturability in the Si foundries⁶. Two of the major issues that have to be addressed while attempting the integration of a different semiconductor on silicon are related to the difference of the thermal expansion, inducing a thermal strain, and to the different lattice parameter and symmetry featured by the epi-layer and the substrate. The latter usually leads to a deformation of the epi-layer lattice, i.e. heteroepitaxial strain, and/or to the formation of non-planar epi-layers featuring a three dimensional morphology not suitable for the fabrication of electronic devices⁷. The heteroepitaxial strain limits the maximum thickness that an epi-layer can feature before its plastic relaxation, i.e. the loss of its in-plane lattice coherence with that of the substrate, through the formation of misfit dislocations (MD)⁸. The formation of the so-called "cross-hatch" pattern (CHP) at the surface of the epilayer is a key signature of the occurrence of the plastic relaxation. The CHP, first observed half a century ago⁹, is now recog-

nized as a common feature for a broad range of heteroepitaxial systems such as InGaAs/GaAs¹⁰, GaAsP/GaAs¹¹, GaAs/Si¹², SiGe/Si¹³, and even IV-VI heteroepitaxial layers¹⁴.

For the common case of growth on (001)- oriented FCC films, the resulting surface morphology is often (i.e. for low misfit, see below) particularly simple, featuring two arrays of lines oriented along two orthogonal [110]-equivalent directions. As this reflects the symmetry of the MD network¹³, a link between the epi-layer morphology and plastic relaxation could be easily argued. However, this one-to-one correlation of the CHP geometry with the MD network is far to be understood, with several experimental observations still remaining unclear. For instance, the distance between adjacent undulations of the CHP, which is not truly periodic, can be orders of magnitude larger than the average distance between dislocations¹⁵. Even the origin of the undulations is still debated. Both bunching of the surface steps produced by the nucleation and gliding of dislocation loops^{15,16}, and the redistribution of surface adatoms induced by inhomogeneities of the strain field at the free surface^{17,18} have been proposed as the root cause for the CHP formation. To our knowledge no quantitative comparison between experimentally observed CHPs and theoretical models is present in the literature.

In this Paper we address and clarify the origin and the dynamics of the CHP by providing a direct, quantitative, time-dependent comparison between a suitable continuum model and dedicated experiments on a low-misfit $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x/\text{Si}(001)$ planar film.

The Paper is organized as follows. In section II our method is introduced, with section IIA dealing about the experimental procedure involved for the growth and characterization of the samples, and section IIB introducing the theoretical model proposed to describe the dynamical evolution of CHPs formation. Results follow

FIG. 1. (color online) Cross-hatch patterns. AFM images obtained for the three sample sets A, B and C described in the text. (a)-(c) AFM after 10 min of annealing for the 600, 1500 and 3000 nm samples respectively. (d)-(f) AFM after 60 min of annealing at 1050°C.

in Sec. III, with a detailed comparison between simulations and experimental results. Conclusions and final remarks are reported in Section IV.

II. METHOD

A. Experimental

A quantitative investigation of a CHP involves the estimation of different morphological parameters, such as the root mean square roughness ρ and the average distance between CHP undulations peaks λ . In general, such quantities depend on several variables, such as the deposition process parameters, the presence of one or more annealing steps, the lattice misfit, the degree of plastic relaxation, and the actual spatial distribution of MD, thus making the result interpretation non-trivial. Therefore, in this work we have designed experiments carefully, in order to analyze the influence of such quantities one at a time. Along this line, we have also minimized the complexity of the CHP by depositing films with a very low misfit f , fixing the Ge content at $x = 0.08$ ($f = 0.0032$). In fact, it is well-known that the number of (semi-) loops in heteroepitaxial layers increases for larger misfit, eventually giving rise to highly entangled distributions of MD which, in turn, are associated to complex surface morphologies displaying no clear CHP. Finally, we investigated the surface morphology evolution using annealing process (rather than during deposition), thereby reducing effects linked to the actual growth kinetics.

The dependence of the CHP on annealing time (10 and 60 min) and on film thickness was analyzed at a given relaxation degree, annealing temperature ($T = 1050^\circ\text{C}$), and (average) dislocation distribution. This was made possible by first growing, by means of a high-temperature CVD process¹⁹, a set of very thick (3000 nm) samples, showing full plastic relaxation, as demonstrated by XRD

measurements. After the growth, we realized three sample sets: A, B, and C. A "gentle" Chemical Mechanical Polishing (CMP) was used on group A, negligibly reducing the film thickness ("gentle" CMP was done using a standard Si process, stopping the process after 10 s, corresponding to a removal of about 20 nm of the SiGe layer). Samples of group B (C), instead, were thinned down by CMP to a thickness of 1500 nm (600 nm). After the CMP process, the roughness of all the samples was in the sub-nm scale, allowing us to rule out any significant role played by step bunches initially present at the free surface in the subsequent evolution.

In Fig. 1 we display Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) images acquired on the various samples in tapping mode using a Bruker Dimension Icon set-up equipped with a closed-loop scanner and using Bruker TESP-SS super sharp tips featuring a 2 nm nominal tip radius. A new tip was used for each individual sample investigated. The surface of all the samples presents a clear CHP, with two sets of perpendicular features aligned along two $[110]$ -equivalent directions. This is interesting per se as CHPs were, so far, observed only after the growth. Here we demonstrate that even if one removes the CHP formed during growth, an annealing following the CMP restores the pattern. Actually, we shall show below that annealing after growth and annealing after growth+CMP lead to almost identical CHPs.

B. Model Definition

The model proposed in this Paper to describe the dynamical evolution of CHPs relies on a continuum 1+1D approach for the morphological evolution of plastically relaxed films, as introduced in Ref.²⁰. This approach describes the surface evolution based on surface diffusion, with the flux of adatoms determined by the gradients in the surface chemical potential μ . The evolution of the surface profile h can be written, in the weak-slope approximation, by projecting the material flux along the vertical direction:

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \nabla M \nabla_s \mu, \quad (1)$$

where M is the adatom mobility and the subscript s denotes the surface gradient operator.

The central quantity in Eq. (1) is the chemical potential which consists of two terms, $\mu = \mu_s + \mu_e$. The first one, μ_s , represents the energy cost associated with the formation of new free surfaces and, for isotropic surface energy density γ , is linearly proportional to the local surface curvature κ , $\mu_s \approx \kappa \gamma$ ²¹. In the following simulations γ was set to 80 meV/Å², typical of Si(001)²². The second term is proportional to the elastic energy density, which can be numerically evaluated by solving partial differential equation for the mechanical equilibrium using the Finite Element Method (FEM) within the linear elasticity

FIG. 2. (color online) Results for an ideal array of 60° dislocations. (a) Surface profile obtained after the annealing of the initially flat film for $t = 5$ a.u. and $t = 50$ a.u. The system has reached an equilibrium: the surface morphology does not evolve anymore upon further annealing. (b) Strain field (ϵ_{xx}) component resulting in a 600 nm -thick film relaxed by an ideal array of 60° dislocations.

framework for isotropic solids. The introduction of the lattice misfit as well as the presence of dislocations in this approach is performed by means of the eigenstrain formalism²³. This allows to take into account dislocations with assigned Burgers vectors and positions (see Ref.²⁰ for further details) by defining an eigenstrain ϵ^* for the epitaxial film: $\epsilon_{ij}^*(x, y) = f\delta_{ij} + \epsilon_{ij}^d(x, y)$, where ϵ^d is the sum of the strain field associated to each individual defect, evaluated by means of analytical expressions²⁴. The total strain used to compute the elastic energy will be then $\epsilon = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T) - \epsilon^*$ with \mathbf{u} the local displacement field obtained by the FEM solution for the elastic problem.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section we shall apply the model described above to a 600 nm-thick $\text{Si}_{0.92}\text{Ge}_{0.08}/\text{Si}(001)$ film, corresponding to the system analyzed in Fig. 1. At first, we considered an array of 60° dislocations, the prevalent type of MD in the low-misfit SiGe/Si material system²⁵, located at the heterointerface, evenly spaced, and with identical Burgers vectors (see schematics in the bottom panel of Fig. 2(a)). The dislocation-dislocation separation is fixed at $d \approx 70$ nm, as required for the complete plastic relaxation of the strain. The simulation cell was set to $L = 1200$ nm and periodic boundary conditions were applied. The initial profile is taken to be perfectly flat, so that the only source of inhomogeneities in the chemical potential is due to the presence of the strain field associated with the network of MD itself, which generates a gradient in the chemical potential. The lat-

ter induces a deformation of the surface profile, which is controlled by the balance between elastic and surface energy. As can be observed in Fig. 2(a), undulations develop and evolve in time until the surface reaches a final equilibrium configuration is reached. Under these ideal conditions the final periodicity matches the one of the underlying MD arrays (Fig. 2(b)). This is in accordance with the static model of Ref.¹⁸, but, evidently, not with the experimental observations of Fig. 1 where the average distance between subsequent undulations is almost two order of magnitude larger, at the micron scale. We checked that the situation does not change if a second, ideal dislocation distribution is considered, consisting of a dislocation distribution where dislocations are still equi-spaced but the orientation of the Burgers vectors is alternated between the two directions available to relax the strain²⁵. Notice that simulations not only predict the wrong periodicity: they strongly underestimate the roughness. Actually, the predicted value has no physical meaning, being much smaller than a single lattice parameter. In summary, Eq. (1) fails in predicting the experimental observations if an ideal distribution of dislocations is considered.

In a recent work (see Ref.²⁵ for details) a detailed analysis of the network of misfit dislocations for thin $\text{Si}_{0.92}\text{Ge}_{0.08}/\text{Si}$ was provided. The nearest-neighbour distance r distribution of the MDs can be very accurately reproduced by a log-normal distribution:

$$f(r) = \frac{1}{r\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp - \frac{(\ln r - \log \alpha)^2}{2\sigma^2} \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2) α represents the logarithm of the mean distance between adjacent MDs, controlling the degree of plastic relaxation introduced by the array of dislocations, while σ represents the dispersion of the distribution. This result, being in agreement with the one already reported in literature by Kaganer et al.¹⁶ for the study of the initial stages of relaxation of a $\text{Si}_{0.4}\text{Ge}_{0.6}/\text{Si}(001)$ system, suggests a possible general behavior. As a consequence we replaced, in the model the ideal distribution with one extracted from Eq. (2), using the same σ value found in²⁵ ($\sigma = 0.7$) and fixing α based on the present dislocation-dislocation distance giving on average full relaxation of the SiGe film ($\log \alpha = 4.2$). The orientation of the individual Burgers vectors was randomly assigned, again following the results of Ref.²⁵.

Simulation results for the three different experimental thicknesses (600 nm, 1500 nm, and 3000 nm) and for different annealing times are reported in Fig. 3²⁶. It is evident that by considering a realistic distribution of dislocations both the typical roughness and the average separation between surface undulations become fully consistent with the experimental findings. Notice that the time scale in the simulations is controlled by the M value of Eq. (1), depending on T ²⁷. As all samples were annealed at the same temperature, a single rescaling factor should be in principle sufficient to match ex-

FIG. 3. (color online) Comparison between simulations and experimental results. (a) rms_{2D}^{26} roughness evolution predicted by the simulations in solid lines and experimental results for the three sample groups A, B, and C (triangle, circle and squares respectively) after 10 and 60 min of annealing. The scan of the experimental surface profiles along one of the two (110) directions for the 600 nm and 3000 nm samples after 60 min of annealing are reported in (b) and (c) and the corresponding simulated profiles are shown in panels (d) and (e).

perimental and simulation times. Indeed, we forced such matching using the two roughness points of the 1500 nm-thick sample, and obtained all other results displayed in Fig.3 (a) with no further readjustment. The overall quantitative, time-dependent agreement between experimental data and simulations is excellent.

Having demonstrated the predictive power of the model, we can now exploit it to directly interpret the interesting physical behavior of the CHP. For instance, the lower ρ value observed for increasing film thickness is readily explained: the dynamics of CHP formation in the model is entirely determined by the magnitude of strain inhomogeneities at the free surface, which is obviously lowered by increasing the film thickness, when the sources of the strain field at the heterointerface get more "buried".

Besides the value of the roughness, the other key quantity characterizing the CHP is the typical distance between surface undulations. In Fig. 3(b)-(c) we report the surface profiles by AFM taken along one of the two equivalent [110] CHP directions, for the 3000 nm-thick sample thinned down to 600 nm and the 3000 nm-thick sample after 60 min of annealing. This can be directly compared with the simulated profiles in panels (d) and (e) for the corresponding two film thicknesses. Albeit qualitatively,

FIG. 4. (color online) Early stages of the surface roughness evolution for the 600 nm sample. (a) and (b) surface profile obtained after the annealing of the initially flat film for $t = 1$ a.u. and $t = 500$ a.u. (c) plot of the surface chemical potential μ presented in panel (c). Furthermore, we report in panel (d) the strain field produced by the MD network in the same $2 \mu\text{m}$ area shaded in panels (a)-(c).

we can clearly see that our model correctly describes the increase of the typical distance between CHP peaks, related to the fading-out of the strain field modulation induced by the MD network in a thicker epi-layer.

The dynamics of the earlier stages of CHP formation for the 600 nm sample can be better appreciated by looking at Fig. 4. The initial response of the system consists in fast-growing high-frequency undulations (panel (a)) that tend to disappear in later stages of the evolution, when larger λ and larger amplitude oscillations develop, as shown in panel (b). This behavior is consistent with the evolution of the surface chemical potential μ presented in panel (c). Furthermore, we report in panel (d) the strain field produced by the MD network in the same $2 \mu\text{m}$ area shaded in panels (a)-(c). The difference with respect to the ideal dislocations distribution can be easily appreciated by comparing it with Fig. 2(b). It is evident that the non-uniform distribution of the dislocation locations gives rise to superpositions of the strain field resulting in the more complex dynamical evolution of the surface profile, finding an equilibrium wavelength λ much larger than the dislocation- dislocation distance.

The above reported analysis was based on annealing of initially flat, fully-relaxed epilayers. This procedure yields clear advantages. We notice, indeed, that CHPs in the literature are usually analyzed directly after growth.

FIG. 5. (color online) Influence of CMP process. AFM images of 600 nm-thick $\text{Si}_{0.92}\text{Ge}_{0.08}$ samples: (a) as-grown reference sample, (b) sample after a 60 min annealing process at 1050°C and (c) sample undertaking a "gentle" CMP before the same 60 minutes annealing process.

As a consequence the observed pattern corresponds to some unknown stages (depending on the deposition conditions) of evolution towards equilibrium, making it very hard to rationalize quantitative estimates in a broader context. Finally, we point out that, at variance with the thinning of the epilayer, the surface smoothing due to the CMP plays no real role in the subsequent evolution of the surface under annealing. This is shown in Fig. 5 where we compare (a) an as-grown 600 nm-thick film ($\lambda = 1.3 \mu\text{m}$ and $\rho = 0.44 \text{ nm}$) with its twin sample annealed for 60 minutes (b) before or (c) after undergoing a "gentle" CMP. The CHP in cases (b) and (c) is almost identical (same $\lambda = 2 \mu\text{m}$ and $\rho = 13.3$ and 13.6 nm respectively), even from the quantitative point of view.

Annealing is thus sufficient to provide a "universal evolution" of the CHP, erasing all possible memory of the evolution stages of the pattern during growth. With this respect, our results are of more general validity.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in this Paper we have shown that a 2D continuum model based on strain-mediated surface diffusion predicts a dynamical evolution of the roughness of low-misfit heteroepitaxial films in good quantitative agreement with experiments. This allows for a direct interpretation of the cross-hatch patterns, here linked to dishomogeneities in the dislocations distribution, half a century after their first observation. Despite being checked by comparison with a specific system, the model is general and is expected to describe a broad class of different (low-misfit) systems.

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²⁶ In order to compare the (2D) experimental results with our (1+1D) simulations we averaged the AFM data of Fig. 1

along one of the two equivalent $\langle 110 \rangle$ directions in a $30 \mu\text{m}$ -wide region, including about 20 CHP wavelenghts for the thinner epilayer and 10 for the thicker one. The rms values obtained after this procedure are indicated in the text as $\text{rms}_{2\text{D}}$.

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